

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were taken on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl_3) taken using TMS as internal standard.

7-n-Butoxy-6-nitroflavone (2a): A mixture of 2'-hydroxy-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrochalcone (**1**; 1 g) and SeO_2 (1 g) in dry n-amyl alcohol (15–20 ml) was refluxed in an oil-bath at 130–40° for 24 h. The precipitated selenium was filtered off and the filtrate steam-distilled to remove n-amyl alcohol. The residual brownish solid was crystallised from ethanol, (65%), m.p. 115° (Found: C, 67.32; H, 5.20; N, 3.9. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_6\text{N}$ calcd. for: C, 67.25; H, 5.01; N, 4.13%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 630 (C=O), 1 550 (C=C) and 1 150 cm^{-1} (C–O–C).

Similarly, other substituted flavones were prepared (**2b–1**; Table 1).

7-n-Butoxy-6-nitroflavonol (3a): It was prepared by the reported method⁴, (80%), m.p. 135° (Found: C, 64.16; H, 4.86; N, 4.0. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_6\text{N}$ calcd. for: C, 64.22; H, 4.78; N, 3.94%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 300 (OH), 1 605 (C=O), 1 560 (C=C) and 1 085 cm^{-1} (C–O–C).

Similarly, other flavonols were prepared (**3b–1**; Table 1).

7-n-Butoxy-6-nitroflavanone (4a): It was prepared by the reported method⁵, (80%), m.p. 118° (Found: C, 66.92; H, 5.51; N, 3.9. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_5\text{N}$ calcd. for: C, 66.86; H, 5.57; N, 4.10%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 690 (C=O) and 1 100 cm^{-1} (C–O–C).

Similarly, other flavanones were prepared (**4b–1**; Table 1).

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Preparation of 5-Methyl-N-propylamino-2,3-dihydroindole Derivatives

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INDOLINES exhibit various biological activities¹ and act as dye². Here, we report the preparation of some of indoline derivatives. *p*-Toluidine was reacted with acrylonitrile to give **2**, which when condensed with chloroacetyl chloride in the presence of triethylamine in benzene followed by reaction with AlCl_3 formed *N*-cyanoethyl-5-methyl-2-oxoindole (**3**). Compound **3** when reduced with LiAlH_4 in THF afforded **4**. The reduction of $-\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ to NH_2 was indicated by the disappearance of ir band at 2 250 cm^{-1} and appearance of a band at 3 200–3 000 cm^{-1} . Various derivatives of **4** were prepared.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 297 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 90 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a EI-MS instrument. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc.

N-Cyanoethyl-p-toluidine (2): *p*-Toluidine (53.5 g, 0.5 mol) and acrylonitrile (26.5 g, 0.5 mol) in acetic acid (2.5 ml) were refluxed for about 15 h and then distilled under reduced pressure. The residue was crystallised with CHCl_3 which on evaporation gave a solid which crystallised from ethanol to yield **2** (36.5 g, 50%), m.p. 102° (Found: C, 82.15; H, 8.13; N, 9.50. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2$ requires: C, 82.19; H, 8.21; N, 9.58%); λ_{max} (ethanol) 265 and 300 nm; ν_{max} (nujol) 3 250 (NH), 2 250 ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$) and 1 600 cm^{-1} (Ph); δ (CCl_4) 2.3 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 2.8 (2H, t, CH_2CN), 3.65 (2H, t, NCH_2), 4.1 (1H, s, NH) and 7.1 (4H, s, ArH).

N-Cyanoethyl-5-methyl-2-oxoindole (3): A mixture of **2** (40 g, 0.5 mol) and chloroacetyl chloride (24 g, 0.5 mol) in benzene (40 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 5 h in the presence of triethyl-

NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4

Compd. no.	R ₁	R ₂	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	$\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) cm^{-1}	δ (TFA)
4a	CH ₃	CH ₃	50	85	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ N ₂	2 900 (OH), 1 600 (C=O)	1.3-1.7 (4H, m, 2×CH ₃), 2.32 (3H, s, ArCH ₃), 2.4-2.6 (2H, t, CH ₂ N), 2.9 (6H, s, 2×NOH ₂), 3.6-3.8 (4H, m, 2×NOH ₂) 6.8-7.8 (3H, m, ArH)
4b	H	CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃	60	220	C ₁₄ H ₂₄ N ₂	3 300-3 200 (NH), 2 900 (OH), 1 600 (C=O)	1-1.2 (3H, t, CH ₃), 1.9-1.7 (6H, m, 3×CH ₂), 2.3 (3H, s, ArCH ₃), 2.4-2.8 (4H, t, 2×CH ₂ N), 3.5-3.8 (4H, t, 2×NOH ₂), 7-7.7 (3H, m, ArH)
4c	H	COCH ₃	68	99	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ ON ₂	3 300-3 250 (NH), 2 900 (OH), 1 600 (C=O), 1 600 (C=O)	1.3-1.7 (4H, m, 2×CH ₃), 2.3 (3H, s, ArCH ₃), 2.5 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 2.6 (2H, t, CH ₂ N), 3.6-3.8 (4H, m, 2×NOH ₂), 7-7.5 (3H, m, ArH), 8.2 (1H, s br, CONH exchangeable with D ₂ O)
4d	H	OPh	70	115	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ ON ₂	3 300-3 200 (NH), 2 900 (OH), 1 670 (C=O), 1 600 (C=O)	1.2-1.65 (4H, m, 2×CH ₃), 2.35 (3H, s, ArCH ₃), 2.6 (2H, t, CH ₂ N), 3.6-3.85 (4H, t, 2×NOH ₂), 6.8-7.8 (3H, m, ArH), 8.2 (1H, s br, CONH exchangeable with D ₂ O)
4e	H	CONHPh	75	52	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ ON ₂	3 300-3 200 (NH), 2 950 (OH), 1 580 (C=O)	1.3-1.75 (4H, m, 2×CH ₃), 2.3 (3H, s, ArCH ₃), 2.4-2.6 (2H, t, CH ₂ N), 3.6 (4H, t, NOH ₂), 7.78 (3H, m, ArH), 8.0 (1H, s br, CONH exchangeable with D ₂ O)
4f	H	OSNHPh	60	200	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₂ S	2 900 (OH), 1 620 (C=C), 1 600 (C=N)	1.25-1.7 (4H, m, 2×CH ₃), 2.35 (3H, s, ArCH ₃), 2.55 (2H, t, CH ₂ N), 3.0 (6H, s, 2×CH ₃), 3.6-3.8 (4H, t, 2×CH ₂), 6.9-7.8 (7H, m, ArH), 8.8 (1H, s, C=CH)
4g	R ₁ =R ₂ =CH.C ₆ H ₄ .N(OH ₂) ₂ (p)		75	65	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ N ₂	2 980 (OH), 1 600 (C=C), 1 580 (C=N)	1.35-1.7 (4H, m, 2×CH ₃), 2.3 (3H, s, ArCH ₃), 2.62 (2H, t, CH ₂ N), 2.9 (6H, s, 2×NOH ₂), 3.2-3.7 (4H, t, 2×NOH ₂), 7-7.8 (7H, m, ArH), 8.8 (1H, s, N=CH)
4h	=CH.C ₆ H ₄ .OH(p)		72	80	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ ON ₂	3 500 (OH), 2 900 (C-H), 1 600 (C=C), 1 580 (C=N)	1.3-1.7 (4H, m, 2×CH ₃), 2.3 (3H, s, ArCH ₃), 2.62 (2H, t, CH ₂ N), 3.5-3.8 (4H, t, 2×NOH ₂), 7-7.8 (7H, ArH), 8.8 (1H, s, N=CH), 9.8 (1H, s, N=CH), 9.8 (1H, s br, OH exchangeable with D ₂ O)
4i	=CH.C ₆ H ₄ .OCH ₃ (p)		65	95	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ ON ₂	2 880 (C-H), 1 600 (C=C), 1 580 (C=N)	1.3-1.7 (4H, m, 2×CH ₃), 2.3 (3H, s, ArCH ₃), 2.62 (2H, t, CH ₂ N), 3.6-3.75 (4H, t, 2×NOH ₂), 3.85 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 6-7.8 (m, ArH), 8.8 (1H, s, N=CH)
4j	=CH.CH=CH.C ₆ H ₅		55	120	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₂	2 900 (C-H), 1 600 (C=C), 1 580 (C=N)	1.3-1.7 (4H, m, 2×CH ₃), 2.3 (3H, s, ArCH ₃), 2.62 (2H, t, CH ₂ N), 3.6-3.75 (4H, t, 2×CH ₂), 6.2-6.4 (2H, dd, J 12 Hz, CH=CH), 7-7.8 (7H, m, ArH), 8.8 (1H, s, N=CH)
4k			60	140	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₂	2 900 (C-H), 1 600 (C=O), 1 580 (C=N)	1.0 (3H, d, CH ₃), 1.1-1.3 (6H, m, 3×CH ₂), 1.3-1.7 (4H, m, 2×CH ₂), 2.2 (2H, t, C=CCH ₂), 2.3 (3H, s, ArCH ₃), 2.6 (2H, t, CH ₂ N), 2.8 (1H, s, OH), 3.6-3.8 (4H, t, 2×NOH ₂), 6.8-7.5 (3H, m, ArH)

(Table 2 contd.)

	R ₁	R ₂					
4l	H	CH ₃ COOC ₂ H ₅	70	125	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂	8 800-8 200 (NH), 2 900 (OH), 1 720 (C=O), 1 600 (C=O)	1.11 (3H, t, CH ₃ ester), 1.3-1.7 (4H, m, 2×CH ₂), 2.3 (3H, s, ArH), 2.6 (2H, t, CH ₂ N), 3.3 (2H, s, NOH ₂ CO), 3.6-3.8 (2H, t, 2×NOH ₂), 4.2 (2H, q, CH ₂ ester), 7-7.8 (3H, m, ArH)
4m			50	90	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₂ O	2 900 (C-H), 1 600 (C=O), 1 580 (C=N)	1-1.1 (6m, m, 2×CH ₂), 1.3-1.7 (4H, m, 2×CH ₂), 2.1 (4H, s, C=CCH ₂), 2.3 (3H, s, ArCH ₃), 2.6 (2H, t, CH ₂ N), 3.65-3.8 (4H, t, 2×NOH ₂), 7-7.8 (3H, m, ArH)

amine (0.5 ml, 0.05 mol). It was then cooled and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The residue was heated with AlCl₃ in CS₂ for 3 h and after removal of the solvent the residue was triturated with ice-cold water to give a insoluble heavy liquid which was purified by distillation under reduced pressure to give 3 (30 g, 60%), b.p. 230° (Found : C, 71.50 ; H, 5.89 ; N, 14.02. C₁₂H₁₂ON₂ requires : C, 72.00 ; H, 6.00 ; N, 14.00%) ; λ_{max} (ethanol) 270 nm ; ν_{max} (nujol) 2 250 (C≡N), 1 700 (C=O) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (Ph) ; δ (TFA) 2.7 (2H, s, CH₂CO), 2.35 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 2.6 (2H, t, CH₂CN), 3.8 (2H, t, NCH₂) and 6.8 (4H, m, ArH).

5-Methyl-N-propylamine-2,3-dihydroindole (4) : Compound 3 (40 g, 0.2 mol) in THF (20 ml) to which LiAlH₄ (7.69 g, 0.2 mol) in THF (15 ml) was added slowly was stirred for about 1.5 h. The mixture was then poured in absolute ethanol to decompose unreacted LiAlH₄ and filtered. After removal of ethanol, the residue was extracted with ether. Ether layer on evaporation gave a solid which was recrystallised from ethanol to give 4 (22.8 g, 50%), m.p. 110° (Found : C, 75.0 ; H, 9.2 ; N, 14.2. C₁₂H₁₅N₂ requires : C, 75.7 ; H, 9.4 ; N, 14.7%) ; λ_{max} (ethanol) 280 nm ; ν_{max} 3 300 (NH₂) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=C) ; δ (TFA) 1.3-1.7 (4H, m, CH₂ and =CCH₂), 2.32 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 2.4-2.6 (2H, m, CH₂N), 3.6-3.8 (4H, m, 3×NCH₂) and 6.85-7.8 (3H, m, ArH) ; M⁺, m/z 190 (1), 173 (100), 160 (12), 146 (10), 132 (20), 120 (75), 105 (55) and 91 (55%).

5-Methyl-N-(N-dimethylaminopropyl)-2,3-dihydroindole (4a) : To a mixture of 4 (0.095 g, 0.0005 mol) and methyl iodide (0.142 g, 0.001 mol) in THF (10 ml), triethylamine (0.2 ml) was added and refluxed for about 5-6 h, then cooled and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The solid obtained was recrystallised from ethanol (4a ; 0.054 g, 50%), m.p. 85°.

Similarly, compounds 4b, 4d and 4e were prepared.

5-Methyl-N-(N-phenylcarbamylaminopropyl)-2,3-dihydroindole (4e) : To a solution of 4 (0.095 g, 0.0005 mol) in THF (10 ml), phenyl isocyanate (0.0595 g, 0.0005 mol) was added over the period of 30 min with stirring and kept overnight. The resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol (4e ; 0.110 g, 75%), m.p. 52°.

Similarly, compound 4f was prepared.

5-Methyl-N-(N-p-dimethylaminobenzilideneaminopropyl)-2,3-dihydroindole (4g) : A mixture of 4 (0.095 g, 0.0005 mol) and p-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.745 g, 0.0005 mol) in THF (10 ml) and a few drops of acetic acid, was refluxed on a water-bath for 5-6 h, then the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. On cooling the separated solid was recrystallised from ethanol (4g ; 0.115 g, 75%), m.p. 65°.

Similarly, compounds 4h-k and 4n were prepared.

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Synthesis of some New 1-Carbamoyl-3-aminophenyl- and 1-Carbamoyl-3-amino-(2-chlorophenyl)- 5-methyl-4-arylazopyrazoles as Possible Potential Antidiabetics

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WIDE range of promising pharmacological activities exhibited by pyrazoles¹ prompted us to synthesise compounds (3) having phenylamino group at position-3 in pyrazole ring.

